

PATERNITY DISPUTES AND DELINQUENT BEHAVIOUR AMONG STREET CHILDREN IN MAJOR TOWNS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Paternity disputes in Nigeria arise due to a parent's suspicious attitude toward a child's behaviour or appearance, especially if the child exhibits traits or characteristics that the parent believes are not consistent with their own. This suspicion may be fueled by doubts about fidelity or the possibility of infidelity during pregnancy. In some cases, the child's physical resemblance to another man or certain behavioural traits may trigger concerns about the child's biological paternity. The implications of this often leads to divorce, stigmatisation, rejection, and forced eviction. This study examined how paternity disputes predisposes street children to delinquent behaviour in major towns in Akwa Ibom State. This study was guided by the assumptions of the Frustration-Aggression Theory, developed by John Dollard, Neal Miller, Leonard Doob, Orval Mowrer, and Robert Sears in 1939, the descriptive survey design was adopted. The research locations were Uyo, Eket, and Ikot Ekpene towns in Akwa Ibom State, and 200 street children aged 7-17 years, who relied on the streets for survival were involved in the study. The stratified, purposive, and convenience sampling techniques were employed in the selection of street children. Data collected through Focused Group Discussions and In-depth Interviews were transcribed and analysed thematically. The results revealed that paternity disputes contributed to street children's susceptibility to delinquent behaviour in major towns in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, by fostering rejection, neglect, and stigmatisation, which led to homelessness, psychological distress, and engagement in delinquent activities as a means of survival and social integration. This study contributes to knowledge by demonstrating the direct impact of paternity disputes on the susceptibility of street children to delinquent behaviour, particularly in the context of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It expands the existing literature on the socio-economic and psychological effects of disputed paternity, providing empirical evidence that rejection, neglect, and stigmatisation stemming from such disputes are key factors that lead to

the displacement of children into the streets. Further research should explore the long-term psychological consequences and the effectiveness of social support programmes to reduce children's vulnerability to homelessness and delinquent behaviour.

Keywords: Paternity Disputes, Street Children, Delinquent Behaviour, Major Towns

Introduction

Paternity disputes have been a global phenomenon with significant social, legal, and psychological implications. Across different regions, these disputes arise due to issues such as infidelity, paternity fraud, reproductive technologies, and legal battles over child custody and support. The consequences of disputed paternity often extend beyond the immediate family, affecting children's identity, emotional well-being, and socio-economic stability (Asangausung, 2024; Efut and Chiagoziem, 2021; Nduna and Jewkes, 2012). In developed countries, paternity disputes are frequently addressed through legal and scientific means, with DNA testing playing a crucial role in resolving uncertainties (Anyogu and Ozioko, 2019; Asangausung, 2024). Many nations, including the United States, Canada, and the United Kingdom, have well-established legal frameworks that mandate paternity testing in cases involving child custody, support, and inheritance rights. Courts often intervene to ensure that children receive financial and emotional support from their biological fathers, reducing the long-term negative impact of such disputes. However, despite the availability of advanced technology, contested paternity can still lead to complex legal battles, emotional distress, and strained family relationships (Hartshorne, 2012).

In contrast, developing countries face additional challenges in handling paternity disputes due to limited access to legal resources, social stigma, and cultural perceptions of fatherhood. In many African and Asian societies, paternity is often linked to marital legitimacy rather than biological proof. As a result, disputes over paternity can lead to the rejection of children, family breakdowns, and in some cases, violence against women accused of infidelity. In countries like Nigeria, paternity disputes are a growing concern, where some men unknowingly raise children who are not biologically theirs, only to discover the truth later through genetic testing. The implications of such discoveries often lead to divorce, disinheritance, and legal battles (Asangausung, 2024). Anyogu and Ozioko (2019) and Ogundipe *et al.* (2019) opined that three out of every ten children are not fathered by men they have seen as their biological fathers in Nigeria.

The issue of street children and juvenile delinquency remains a significant social challenge in Nigeria, particularly in urban areas where economic hardship and family instability are prevalent (Ukommi, 2023; Mboho and Ndaeyo, 2019; Mboho and Udousoro, 2014). Among the numerous factors contributing to this phenomenon, disputed paternity has emerged as a critical but often overlooked determinant. In countries like Nigeria, paternity disputes are a growing concern, where some men unknowingly raise children who are not biologically theirs. Paternity disputes can arise due to a parent's suspicious attitude toward a child's behaviour or appearance, especially if the child exhibits traits or characteristics that the parent believes are not consistent with their own. This suspicion may be fueled by doubts about fidelity or the possibility of infidelity during pregnancy. In some cases, the child's physical resemblance to another man or certain behavioural traits may trigger concerns about the child's biological paternity (Asangausung, 2024).

The implications of this often lead to divorce, disinheritance, and legal battles. These

suspicious can lead to a breakdown in trust between the parents, causing emotional distress for both the child and the adults involved. The child may feel unwanted or unloved, and in some instances, the tension surrounding the paternity dispute can escalate to outright rejection or neglect (Mboho and Udo, 2013). The situation can have long-lasting psychological effects on the child, potentially leading to feelings of confusion, identity issues, and vulnerability to delinquent behaviour as they seek to understand their place within the family or society (Obalowu and Rahim, 2022).

Paternity disputes create emotional, psychological, and economic instability, leading to family breakdown and neglect, which in turn push many children into the streets. Asangausung (2024) defined “street children” as children who permanently reside on the streets and rely on the street for survival. These individuals spend a great deal of their time in public areas such as flyovers, streets, motor parks, Ibom Plaza, and other urban infrastructure. Without proper parental care and support, these children face extreme vulnerabilities, including poverty, hunger, social stigma, and exposure to criminal influences. The lack of a stable identity and familial acceptance often fosters frustration, resentment, and a struggle for survival, increasing their susceptibility to delinquent behaviours such as theft, substance abuse, gang involvement, and many others (Asangausung *et al.*, 2023).

Despite growing concerns about the increasing number of street children in major towns of Akwa Ibom State, limited attention has been given to the role of disputed paternity in predisposing these children to delinquent behaviour. Family instability resulting from paternity disputes often leads to the rejection and neglect of children, forcing them into environments where they must fend for themselves. The psychological effects of being unwanted, coupled with economic deprivation and lack of guidance, create conditions that encourage criminal activity as a means of survival. Asangausung (2024) avers that delinquent behaviour constitutes the actions of street children that go against state legislation as well as social norms. Among the specific signs of delinquent behaviour in street children include stealing, property damage or vandalism, drug and alcohol abuse, drug distribution, gangsterism, begging, gambling, vagrancy, fighting, and sexual activity.

Previous studies have focused on broader issues such as paternity fraud, marital infidelity, and family breakdown but have not adequately explored how paternity disputes specifically influences the behavioural outcomes of affected children. For instance, Obalowu and Rahim (2022) examined marital infidelity and paternity dispute in Nigeria using Islamic perspective. Efut and Chiagoziem (2021) investigated the primary causes of paternity fraud and strategies for compensating its victims. Nduna and Jewkes (2012) examined rejected paternity in teenage pregnancies in the Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. However, none of these studies was conducted in Akwa Ibom State, particularly on how disputed paternity contributes to street children's vulnerability to delinquent behaviour. This gap in research necessitates an in-depth investigation into how disputed paternity contributes to street children's vulnerability to delinquent behaviour in major towns in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The underlying question is: How does paternity disputes affect street children's vulnerability to delinquent behaviour?

Literature Review

Obalowu and Rahim (2022) examined marital infidelity and paternity dispute in Nigeria using Islamic perspective. Utilising a qualitative approach, the data were gathered from appropriate sources through sufficient analysis of the literature reviewed. The findings

indicated that the main cause of the pervasive marital infidelity was linked to the prevalent, non-Islamic practice of establishing affairs between the sexes through premarital relationships and closeness with the other sex, which typically lasts beyond a formal marriage. It further revealed that Islamic law holds that an adulterer cannot be granted fatherhood and that a child born under his conjugal custody cannot have its legal paternity denied by a DNA test or any other kind of evidence. The study by Obalowu and Rahim (2022) on marital infidelity and paternity disputes from an Islamic perspective lacks a focus on the social, psychological, and behavioural consequences on children, particularly street children in Nigeria. The study highlights the broader societal impact of these disputes, including lack of family support and security.

Efut and Chiagoziem (2021) examined the primary causes of paternity fraud and strategies for compensating its victims in Nigeria. The study used a survey research method that employed both primary and secondary data. The primary data were obtained using the open-ended questionnaire. Tables and simple percentages were employed to analyse the data. The findings revealed that paternity fraud is common in Nigeria, and that the main factors causing paternity fraud in Nigeria were pressure from marriages seeking to grow their family, the mistake of exchanging children, and instances of unintended births. The study primarily investigates paternity fraud causes and compensation in Nigeria; but does not specifically examine how disputed paternity predisposes children to delinquent behaviour, focusing on its impact on family dynamics and child development.

Nduna and Jewkes (2012) used semi-structured interviews in a small rural community in the Eastern Cape Province, South Africa, to examine rejected paternity in teenage pregnancies. The research revealed that the boyfriends of the participants were involved in different types of denial and arguments regarding their pregnancies. The males were temporary suspects because they denied responsibility, moved, and expressed disbelief when they learnt of the pregnancy. For their careless behaviour, not using contraception, and getting pregnant, the participants believed that being told they were not pregnant was a punishment. The individuals were upset by ongoing concern over the undetermined paternity. The study by Nduna and Jewkes (2012) explores rejected paternity in teenage pregnancies in South Africa. However, it lacks comprehensive investigation into its impact on children's psychological well-being and behavioural outcomes. The research could address this gap by examining how children born from rejected paternity experience familial instability, loss of paternal involvement, stigma, and social exclusion.

In summary, of the reviewed literature explores different aspects of paternity disputes, including marital infidelity, paternity fraud, and rejected paternity, but none directly examines how disputed paternity influences street children's susceptibility to delinquent behaviour. Obalowu and Rahim (2022) focus on marital infidelity and paternity disputes from an Islamic perspective, highlighting legal and religious implications but overlooking the social, psychological, and behavioural consequences for children, particularly those who end up on the streets. While the study emphasis the broader societal impact, it does not explore how these children cope with family rejection and instability.

Efut and Chiagoziem (2021) investigate the causes of paternity fraud and strategies for compensating victims, identifying factors such as marital pressure, child exchange errors, and unintended births as key contributors. However, their study primarily addresses the issue from an adult perspective, neglecting how disputed paternity affects children's psychological well-being and their likelihood of engaging in delinquent activities due to family breakdown

and lack of support. Nduna and Jewkes (2012) examine rejected paternity in teenage pregnancies in South Africa, revealing patterns of paternal denial and its emotional toll on young mothers. Although the study touches on the distress caused by paternity disputes, it does not investigate the long-term consequences on children born under such circumstances, particularly how familial instability, stigma, and lack of paternal involvement shape their behaviour and social adaptation.

The implications of the reviewed literature for the current study highlight a significant gap in understanding how disputed paternity contributes to delinquency among street children. While previous studies focus on the causes and broader implications of paternity disputes, they do not directly link these disputes to children's live experiences, particularly their vulnerability to street life and delinquent behaviour. The current study fills this gap by examining how the absence of paternal recognition, rejection, and family instability drive children toward survival mechanisms that increase their risk of engaging in delinquent behaviour. Understanding these dynamics can provide valuable insights for policymakers, social workers, and child welfare Organisations seeking to develop interventions that address the root causes of delinquency among street children affected by disputed paternity.

Theoretical Framework

The Frustration-Aggression Theory

The Frustration-Aggression Theory, proposed by John Dollard, Neal Miller, Leonard Doob, Orval Mowrer, and Robert Sears in 1939, suggests that when individuals are prevented from achieving their goals, they experience frustration, which in turn leads to aggressive behaviour (Asangausung et al., 2024). The fundamental assumption of the theory is that frustration arises when individuals face obstacles that block their needs or desires, and this frustration can manifest as aggression if no alternative coping mechanisms are available. It also suggests that repeated frustration without resolution can lead to displaced aggression, where individuals direct their frustration toward weaker targets or engage in deviant behaviour as an outlet. However, Leonard Berkowitz in 1989 modified the theory, arguing that frustration does not always lead to aggression but creates a readiness for aggression, which is triggered by environmental cues.

In applying this theory to the study of how disputed paternity contributes to street children's susceptibility to delinquent behaviour in major towns in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, disputed paternity creates an environment where children experience rejection, neglect, and emotional instability. Many of these children face stigmatisation, lack of parental care, and economic hardship, all of which contribute to deep-seated frustration. The inability to access basic needs, education, and familial support increases their vulnerability, leading them to develop aggressive or delinquent behaviours as coping mechanisms. Without proper guidance or support, these children may resort to theft, gang involvement, or substance abuse as expressions of their frustration. The theory helps to explain why children affected by disputed paternity are more likely to engage in delinquency, as their frustration over abandonment and social exclusion manifests in aggression toward society or survival-driven criminal activities. This underscores the importance of addressing the emotional and social needs of such children to prevent the cycle of frustration leading to aggression and delinquency.

Methodology

The study investigated street children in Uyo, Eket, and Ikot Ekpene towns of Akwa Ibom State using a descriptive survey design. The towns were chosen due to their high concentration of street children. Akwa Ibom State was created in 1987, has 31 local government areas and borders the Gulf of Guinea, Abia State, Cross River State, and Rivers State. Akwa Ibom State has a high concentration of street children (Ekpenyong and Udisi, 2016) due to high rates of poverty (Etim, 2023). The economy of the state is based on agriculture, fishing, trading, and civil service jobs. The state is rich in cultural heritage. This study used mixed methods to gather data from street children in Eket, Ikot Ekpene, and Uyo towns, focusing on those living without parental support. The target group was children aged 7-17, who were experts in their experiences and challenges. The study excluded street children under 7 and above 18 years. According to Ukpong (2021), statistics on the number of street children in Akwa Ibom State are unknown.

The study involved 200 street children aged 7-17 from Uyo, Eket, and Ikot Ekpene towns. The sample size was determined through data redundancy or saturation, rather than using a statistical technique. 19 focus group discussions and 29 in-depth interviews were conducted with the children. The determination of sample size through data redundancy or saturation is supported by Rahimi and Khatooni (2024), Daher (2023), Henninck and Kaiser (2021), and Glasser and Strauss (2017). The study used stratified, purposive, and convenience sampling techniques to select street children in Uyo, Eket, and Ikot Ekpene towns in Akwa Ibom State. The towns were chosen based on the large number of street children in each district.

Table 1: Sample allocation according to LGAs and methods of data collection

Study Location	FGD	IDI	Total
Uyo Town	72	13	85
Eket Town	45	6	51
Ikot Ekpene Town	54	10	64
Total	171	29	200

Source: Field data (2025).

Table 1 shows the sample distribution according to LGAs and data collection techniques. Out of the 200 street children who live constantly on the streets without their parents or guardians, 85 of them were from Uyo town, 51 were from Eket town and 64 of them were from Ikot Ekpene town. Twenty-nine (29) street children participated in the In-Depth Interviews (IDIs), while 171 street children participated in the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). The participants were interviewed through Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and In-Depth Interviews (IDIs). The socio-demographic information was collected prior to the interviews, and the interviews were conducted in Ibibio, Annang, and Ekid languages. Three research assistants were engaged to gather primary data. The qualitative data were analysed through thematic analysis, with the transcribed data serving as the basis for the analysis. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethical and Attitudinal Reorientation Commission and a letter of introduction from the Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Welfare. Data collection was challenging due to the children's wandering demographic status. All street children provided oral consent, were informed of their right to confidentiality and privacy, and prioritized their comfort, safety, and autonomy to reduce exploitation risks.

Results

The socio-demographic characteristics of the 200 study participants as well as their family situations before they resorted to street life shown that the majority of the street children were male (79.5%), while females made up only 20.50 per cent, which suggests that street life disproportionately affected boys in the selected towns. The distribution of children by town indicates that Uyo, the capital of Akwa Ibom State, has the highest concentration of street children (42.5%), followed by Ikot Ekpene (32%) and Eket (25.5%), which might reflect the urbanisation and social dynamics of these towns. The age distribution reveals that the majority of street children are within the younger age brackets; 30 per cent are between 7 and 9 years old, and 28.50 per cent are between 10 and 12 years old, which could suggest that early exposure to the harsh realities of street life is common. The relatively small percentage of older children (17.5% between 16 and 17 years) indicates that many children are likely to start their street life at a very young age.

Educationally, a significant portion of the children (25%) have never attended school, while 40.5% have not completed primary school, suggesting that educational deprivation is a major factor in their vulnerability. Interestingly, no child in the sample has completed secondary school, underscoring the stark lack of educational opportunities for these children, which often correlates with higher susceptibility to delinquent behaviour due to limited life options.

The custodial role before the children took to street life reveals significant family instability. A large proportion of the children (45.5%) were primarily under the care of a step-parent, while 27.5% were cared for by their fathers, and 7% by their mothers. The fact that so many children had step-parents in charge suggests a disrupted family structure, which may be closely linked to the conditions that contribute to their street life. The absence of consistent and nurturing parental care, coupled with potential neglect or abuse by step-parents, can be a contributing factor to the children's involvement in delinquency as they seek survival or identity outside of the family.

The significant of the socio-demographic data points to a clear relationship between family instability, lack of education, and the vulnerability of street children to delinquent behaviour. The high number of children living under the care of step-parents and the lack of educational achievement suggest that these factors could be contributing to their involvement in criminal activities. The data supports the popular opinion that disputed paternity and family breakdown are key elements influencing the susceptibility of these children to delinquency.

Analysis of Qualitative Data

The research revealed that street children with paternity disputes often engage in delinquent behaviour due to harsh conditions, lack of parental support, and social stigma. These children resort to theft, drug use, or gang involvement for survival. The absence of positive role models and guidance further contributes to their delinquent behaviour, leading to emotional instability, aggression, anxiety, and depression. When asked about how they were treated at home before they resorted to life on the street, one of the street children said:

“I was often ignored and maltreated, which made me feel like I didn't belong to the family, pushing me to seek acceptance elsewhere...” (FGD/male/aged 12/Uyo/January 10, 2025).

This response demonstrated the emotional and social alienation experienced by children of disputed paternity, which increases their susceptibility to delinquent behaviour.

Neglect and mistreatment at home foster feelings of rejection, low self-worth, and isolation, leading them to seek belonging in external environments, often among peers who engage in delinquent activities.

Another street child said:

“My mother's family constantly reminded me of my birth status, and it made me feel unloved and unwanted...” (FGD/male/aged 15/Uyo/January 12, 2025).

The emotional impact of disputed paternity stigmatization is profound, causing feelings of alienation, rejection, and low self-esteem. This neglect can lead a child to seek acceptance and identity in street life. The study highlights the impact of family dynamics and stigma on children's behaviour, emphasizing the need for understanding these pathways.

Furthermore, a 13-year-old street child said,

“I am a victim of step-parenting. At the moment, I don't have a father, and my mother is married to another man. I was told that my mother was raped by my supposed father, and I was abandoned at the age of 5. Since then, I have remained a permanent street child...” (FGD/male/Uyo/January 15, 2025).

The response highlights the profound consequences of paternity disputes, especially when linked to traumatic circumstances like rape, and the impact on a child's life. The child's abandonment at an early age highlights the failure of familial and societal support systems, making street life a necessity rather than a choice. Unresolved paternity disputes contributed significantly to the vulnerability of street children.

Yet, another street child said;

“I was treated like a burden, and they always used derogatory words about me, saying that I am a bastard because I was born out of wedlock and without any traceable paternity...” (FGD/male/aged 10/Eket/January 20, 2025).

The response reveals the damaging effects of stigma and verbal abuse on children of disputed paternity. The statement highlights the emotional and psychological distress caused by constant rejection and dehumanization. Being labelled as illegitimate and without a traceable paternity, reinforces a deep sense of isolation and unworthiness, which can push a child away from the family structure and into the streets in search of acceptance. For the study, these accounts demonstrated how disputed paternity can lead to persistent discrimination and emotional neglect, increasing the likelihood of children becoming street-involved. The negative labels and exclusion from family support systems create an environment where delinquency becomes more probable, as these children may engage in deviant behaviour to cope with their marginalization.

Another street child said;

“I felt like I was always treated differently because of the issues that surrounded my birth. It was hard to form close relationships with my mother's relatives...” (FGD/male/aged 8/Ikot Ekpene/January 25, 2025).

The response revealed the emotional isolation and exclusion experienced by children of disputed paternity within their own families. The statement suggests that the child was subjected to discrimination and unequal treatment due to the circumstances of their parentage. The difficulty in forming close relationships with maternal relatives indicates a

lack of emotional support, further deepening the child's sense of alienation. For the study, this account emphasises how disputed paternity disrupts family bonds and contributes to a child's vulnerability. The feeling of being different and unwelcome can push a child toward street life in search of belonging and companionship. Without a supportive family network, these children are at higher risk of engaging in delinquent behaviour as a means of survival or coping with emotional distress.

Yet, another street child said;

“I was abandoned without protection and care because my paternity cannot be traced. I hate my mother that brought me to this world...” (IDI/male/aged 16/Ikot Ekpene/January 31, 2025).

The response demonstrated the emotional and psychological impact of paternity disputes, particularly in children who experience abandonment and lack of parental support. This lack of support leads to homelessness and vulnerability to delinquency, as children often turn to street life for coping and sustaining themselves, underscoring the importance of unresolved paternity disputes in Akwa Ibom State.

When asked about how their condition of paternity disputes caused them to indulge in delinquent behaviour, one of the street children said;

“I was neglected and had to fend for myself, which made me turn to stealing and other illegal activities...” (FGD/male/aged 13/Uyo/January 10, 2025).

The street child's experience of disputed paternity is linked to delinquent behaviour, as they feel neglected and need to fend for themselves. This neglect, often due to family conflict or lack of support, can lead to criminal behaviour. The absence of a reliable father figure creates emotional and financial insecurity, influencing the child's decision to seek illegal means of survival.

Another street child said;

“Feeling like I didn't belong to any family led me to join gangs and engage in risky behaviour to find a sense of identity and acceptance...” (FGD/male/aged 16/Uyo/January 12, 2025).

The response revealed that paternity disputes affect a street child's sense of identity and belonging, leading to an emotional void they fill through risky behaviours and gang involvement. This lack of a stable family structure makes these children more susceptible to delinquent behaviour, as they seek validation through alternative sources of identity, often involving risky or illegal activities. The psychological consequences of disputed paternity contributed to the development of delinquent behaviour in street children.

Yet, another street child said;

“Vulnerability and fear made me seek protection from older criminals, leading to my involvement in drug use, thievery, and gang groups...” (FGD/male/aged 17/Uyo/January 15, 2025).

The street child's response highlights the emotional and psychological impact of disputed paternity, leading to increased vulnerability and fear. This vulnerability often leads to seeking security from external sources, such as older criminals, which can lead to drug use, theft, and gang involvement. The psychological effects of paternity disputes can result in children making choices based on survival instincts, further deepening their involvement in delinquent behaviour.

Furthermore, a street child said;

“Shame and ridicule drove me to bully others, get involved in petty theft, and act as a lookout for burglars...” (FGD/male/aged 10/Eket/January 16, 2025).

The above response reveals that paternity disputes can lead to a child's delinquent behaviour due to feelings of shame and ridicule. This humiliation, possibly due to rejection or stigma, can cause the child to seek power or control to cope with feelings of inadequacy or low self-worth. This can result in behaviours like bullying and crime, as the child seeks validation from peers and a sense of belonging. The psychological consequences of disputed paternity can significantly contribute to a child's susceptibility to delinquent behaviour.

A street child added;

“Confusion and lack of guidance led me to get involved in petty theft, and drug abuse to escape reality, also engage in scrap-picking activities to make some money...” (FGD/male/aged 10/Eket/January 20, 2025).

The street child's response highlights the confusion and lack of guidance due to disputed paternity, leading to poor decision-making and emotional strain. They resort to petty theft, drug abuse, and scrap-picking as coping mechanisms, despite their destructive nature. The study suggests that disputed paternity can lead children down to delinquency paths, as they struggle to navigate life without a stable family structure, particularly the father figure. These behaviours further distanced them from positive development.

Another street child said;

“I was stigmatised and not properly fed. This condition led me to move to the streets to beg and sometimes steal to stay alive...” (FGD/male/aged 11 /Ikot Ekpene/January 25, 2025).

Street children face stigma and lack of basic needs due to disputed paternity, leading to feelings of exclusion and vulnerability. Lack of nutrition exacerbates their vulnerability, leading them to seek survival on the streets. Begging and stealing becomes their coping strategies, driven by emotional and physical neglect. This neglect increases their susceptibility to delinquency, as they must make difficult choices to meet their immediate needs.

Yet, another street child said;

“My late mother told me that I was born out of rape. She hates me very much and refused to take any responsibility concerning me. I beg people for survival. Sometimes I do steal people's things because life is not easy...” (IDI/male/aged 12/Ikot Ekpene/January 31, 2025).

The street child's emotional and psychological trauma, exacerbated by disputed paternity, leads to a sense of worthlessness and isolation. The child resorts to begging and stealing as survival strategies, reflecting their frustration with life's harshness and lack of support. The psychological trauma and lack of parental support made these children to be highly vulnerable to delinquent behaviour. The study highlights the importance of family structure and support in preventing delinquency, as these children seek to navigate a world of neglect and stigmatisation.

Discussions

The results showed that paternity disputes contributed to street children's

susceptibility to delinquent behaviour in major towns in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, by fostering rejection, neglect, and stigmatisation, which lead to homelessness, psychological distress, and engagement in criminal activities as a means of survival and social integration. Due to a variety of psychological, social, educational, and financial difficulties, street children are more likely to engage in delinquent activity when their paternity is disputed. To cope with their emotional suffering and stress, a lot of street children with contested paternity concerns turned to stealing, scrap-picking, drug usage and trafficking, begging, and other deviant habits. The finding is supported by Asangausung (2024), Obalowu and Rahim (2022), Efut and Chiagoziem (2021), and Anyogu and Ozioko (2019), who all documented that children of disputed paternity are susceptible to living on the streets, and that their chances of surviving depends on their involvement in delinquent behaviour.

Paternity disputes play a crucial role in increasing the likelihood that street children will engage in delinquent behaviour, stemming from a confluence of emotional, social, economic, and educational challenges. The uncertainty and instability associated with disputed paternity often leave children grappling with profound emotional issues, including a lack of self-worth and identity confusion. These emotional scars can lead to a sense of alienation and rejection, pushing them toward delinquent behaviour as a way to cope with their inner turmoil.

Socially, the disruption caused by paternity disputes can strain family relationships, leading to a lack of support and guidance. This family instability often results in social isolation and stigma, further alienating these children from their peers and the broader community. As a consequence, they might turn to street life and form connections with negative peer groups, which can reinforce and escalate their engagement in criminal activities. Economically, children with disputed paternity frequently face poverty and financial instability. The absence of consistent parental support can force them into survival strategies such as begging, theft, or drug trafficking. Economic hardship severely limits their access to basic necessities and opportunities, pushing them towards illegal means of sustenance and income.

Educationally, the combined impact of emotional and economic challenges often disrupts their schooling. Without proper support and resources, these children may struggle academically, leading to school dropouts and diminished future prospects. This educational failure further exacerbates their vulnerability, as they may perceive delinquent activities as viable alternatives or coping mechanisms in the face of their educational struggles. Children facing disputed paternity often experience feelings of abandonment, rejection, and low self-worth. These emotional struggles can lead to anger, frustration, and a lack of trust in others, which are common precursors to delinquent behaviour. The absence of a confirm father figure often results in a lack of appropriate parental guidance and supervision. Without a stable and supportive home environment, children are more likely to seek acceptance and belonging through negative peer influences, such as gangs or criminal groups.

Many children affected by disputed paternity face economic deprivation. This often forces them to engage in activities such as begging, scrap picking, or petty theft to meet their basic needs. This lack of financial stability and support exacerbates their vulnerability to delinquency. Children born out of wedlock often face social stigma and discrimination within their communities and families. This marginalisation can lead to social isolation and a sense

of alienation, pushing children towards delinquent behaviour as a means of coping or gaining attention. The instability caused by disputed paternity frequently results in disrupted education. Children who are not regularly attending school miss out on critical development milestones and educational opportunities, increasing the likelihood of engaging in delinquent behaviour.

The issue of DNA test to proof paternity is a serious factor to the rise of street children. DNA paternity testing provides an invaluable tool for men who fear they may not be the father of any of their children. The marriage might fail when this confirmation is made. If the marriage continues, the male can get extremely resentful and take it out on the child, which might have a long-lasting effect on the child. However, for individuals who impregnate girls and women while denying culpability, the consequences of DNA paternity testing can be profound. Too many girls have been left useless by the responsibilities of unexpected pregnancy. Women suffer the most when a man speaks negatively about the woman who is carrying her unborn child. Though such a child is customarily considered to be part of the mother's family, the DNA paternity test will help determine who the child's father is, at the very least. When the father admits to being the child's father, the youngster no longer bears the label "bastard", as the DNA test makes it impossible for him to continue denying the child's paternity. Children without a biological father ought not to be allowed to roam the streets without adequate protection and care.

In summary, the combination of these factors creates a precarious environment for street children with disputed paternity. The lack of stable emotional, social, economic, and educational support drives them towards various forms of delinquency as they seek to manage their challenging circumstances.

Conclusion

The study examined how paternity disputes predisposes street children to delinquent behaviour in major towns in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The result demonstrated that paternity disputes contributed to street children's susceptibility to delinquent behaviour in major towns in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, by fostering rejection, neglect, and stigmatisation, which lead to homelessness, psychological distress, and engagement in criminal activities as a means of survival and social integration.

This study enhances understanding of the link between paternity disputes and street children's vulnerability to delinquent behaviour in major towns in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. By demonstrating that rejection, neglect, and stigmatisation resulting from paternity disputes contributed to homelessness and psychological distress, the study provides empirical evidence on how family instability directly influences juvenile delinquency. It expands the discourse on child welfare by emphasising the role of disputed paternity as a social determinant of delinquent behaviour, highlighting the need for policy interventions that address the consequences of parental rejection and abandonment.

Future studies should explore the long-term psychological effects of disputed paternity on children's emotional and behavioural development, assessing how experiences of rejection shape their life trajectories. A comparative study between children affected by paternity disputes and those raised in stable family structures could provide deeper insights into coping mechanisms and resilience. Additionally, further research should evaluate the effectiveness of existing legal and social support systems in mitigating the adverse effects of paternity disputes, with a focus on intervention programmes that promote child protection,

rehabilitation, and social reintegration.

Recommendation

To address the issue of paternity disputes predisposing street children to delinquent behaviour in major towns in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, several measures should be taken. First, awareness campaigns should be conducted to educate parents and communities on the psychological and social consequences of rejecting children due to disputed paternity, emphasising the importance of providing emotional and financial support regardless of paternity uncertainties.

Legal frameworks should be strengthened to ensure that children affected by paternity disputes receive adequate protection, with laws enforcing parental responsibility and discouraging abandonment. Government and non-governmental organisations should establish more child welfare programs, including shelters, counseling services, and skills acquisition centers, to support children who experience neglect and homelessness as a result of paternity disputes.

Family mediation and conflict resolution services should be promoted to help resolve disputes amicably and prevent situations where children become victims of parental disagreements. Furthermore, the government should implement policies that encourage responsible parenting, including free or subsidized DNA testing for low-income families to prevent wrongful rejection of children based on suspicion.

Lastly, the education system should integrate social and emotional learning programmes to equip children affected by family instability with coping mechanisms, reducing their likelihood of engaging in delinquent behaviour. Strengthening community-based interventions that foster inclusivity and support for vulnerable children will also help mitigate the risks associated with paternity disputes.

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